

THE EXTENT OF THE STUDY OF WORD-FORMATION AND AFFIXATION BY CHINESE LINGUISTS

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ABSTRACT

The need for language teaching and learning is ever increasing in today's idealize and creating countries. There's moreover a developing interest in learning foreign languages in Uzbekistan, as well as the life, culture and history of these languages. Words develop in accordance with the language development laws. However, they are not the same in all languages. Accordingly, it is important to memorize such tools on the basis of the rules of each language. On this basis, our investigate work looked for to cover the issue of word formation using the affixation method, which could be a morphological method in Chinese and Indonesian.

Key words. *Lexical morphema, affix affixing lexeme, substance of compound, syntactic, morphological, neologisms' vocabulary, prefixes and half prefixes, suffixes and half suffixes, infixes, morphological-syntactic, motphological-phonetic, lexical-symantic method, redublication and contraction.*

Introduction. The need for language teaching and learning is ever increasing in today's perfect and developing countries. There is also a growing interest in learning foreign languages in Uzbekistan, as well as the life, culture and history of these languages. In recent years, our government has taken many measures to study the language, history, culture, and people's lives of the China and countries of South East Asia. All of this is indicative of a strong focus on the supply of Chinese specialists and Indonesians, language specialists, teachers and translators in Uzbekistan.

Creating a word means creating a new word in some way. The new word is usually formed in the language with the help of word-formation tools. New words complement and improve the dictionary. Words develop in accordance with the language development laws. However, they are not the same in all languages. Accordingly, it is important to learn such tools on the basis of the rules of each language. On this basis, our research work sought to cover the issue of word formation using the affixation method, which is a morphological method in Chinese and Indonesian, which is two different families.

The word-making model consists of three parts:

- 1) lexical morpheme that forms the basis of word-formation;
- 2) affix affixing lexeme - formative affix or formant;
- 3) nature, substance of compound formation.

A variety of lexicon-changing formants were observed in Chinese and Indonesian.

Method. Some methods of modern Chinese word-making in the works of V. M. Solntsev described in detail how conversions, words, and affixes are used. In the Chinese language, Gorelov distinguishes lexical-semantic, lexical-morphological, morphological, morphological-syntactic, morphological-phonetic, lexical-semantic methods, reduplication and contraction. O. P. Frolova studies the problem of nouns in terms of terminology and defines morphological, syntactic, phonetic methods and conversion. In his research with, morphological, semantic, and affective vocabulary are described, detailing the contractions of morpheme and its types.

Result. Chinese linguists Li Jinxing and Liu Shiju cite three main ways of word formation:

Syntactic - (成分结构 *chengfen jiegou*, or 句法构词法 *jufa goucifa*);

Morphological – (形态结构 *xingtai jiegou*, or 形态构词法 *xingtai goucifa*);

Phonetic – (语音结构 *yuyin jiegou*, or 语音构词法 *yuyin goucifa*).

Li Jinxing and Liu Shiju understand that morphology is the creation of new words through affixation and reduplication. (桌子 *zhuozi* – table, 老虎 *laohu*– tiger, 时时 *shishi*– always).

According to Sun Chansu, morphological-structural (structural) methods include word formation using affixation (老鼠 *laoshu* – mouse, rat, 爱好者 *aihaozhe* – amateur male, amateur woman) and phonetic modifications (such as the author of the classification, 吏 *li* – word of servant, junior official and 事 *shi*– as a result of the phonetic process of the word work 史 *shi* – derived from the word history).

Morphological 词法学造词法 *cifaxue zaocifa* ;

Syntactic 句法学造词法 *jufaxue zaocifa*;

Stylistic 修辞学造词法 *xiucixue zaocifa* ;

Phonetic 语音学造词法 *yuyinxue zaocifa*;

Synthetic 综合式造词法 *zongheshi zaocifa*

The author introduces the morphological method of word formation: affixation, reduplication, phonetic modification and conversion (转类式).

Jen Syuelyan divides adjectives into words by using prefixes, suffixes, and infixes, as well as a few suffixes (多重词尾– *duozhong ciwei*) and counting words (加量词– *jialiangci*). The author examines 18 prefixes in his monograph, noting that in

recent decades Chinese prefixes have emerged from independent words and have not lost their lexical meaning. These prefixes include:

老 lao, 阿 a, 小 xiao, 可 ke, 第 di, 初 chu, 巴 ba, 反 fan, 被 bei, 见 jian, 所 suo, 而 er, 非 fei, 不 bu, 准 zhun, 二 er, 以 yi

In describing the use of suffixes, Jeng Xuelyan states that the suffixes in the Chinese language are much higher than the prefixes, using nouns, verbs, and adjectives. Like prefixes, suffixes are formed from words with independent meaning, and not all of them have lost their lexical meaning. Jen Suuelyan makes the following words in the word suffix: 子 zi, 儿 er, 头 tou, 员 yuan, 家 jia, 者 zhe, 士 shi, 师 shi, 生 sheng, 手 shou, 汉 han, 夫 fu, 丁 ding, 郎 lang, 众 zhong, 属 shu, 鬼 gui, 棍 gun, 迷 mi, 犯 fan, 派 pai, 分子 fenzi, 主义 zhuyi, 性 xing, 处 chu, 品 pin, 巴 ba, 化 hua, 于 yu, 乎 hu, 以 yi, 么 me, 然 ran, 其 qi, 切 qie, 而 er, 尔 er, 且 qie, 的 de, 地 di, 得 de, 了 liao (le), 着 zhe.

The author then cites examples of quasisuffixes, or suffix-like words, explaining that such suffixes (准词尾 – zhunciwei) are in the process of development and that they are very numerous: 论 lun, 度 du, 式 shi, 却 que, 豪 hao.

Discussion. Although the author of the classification considers the formation of words by counting words as a particular form of word-formation, he studies them within the context of affect. Its peculiarity is that as a result of adding a noun account, one word joins into two syllables, using only the nouns. For example: 花朵 huaduo – flowers, 信件 xinjian – letters, 船只 chuanzhi – ships, fleet. Analyzing the word-formation classification above, it should be noted that all three authors distinguish between phonetic and morphological methods in modern Chinese (Sun Chansu's method is morphologically-structured), but these terms have different meanings. For example, in the interpretation of Li Jinji and Liu Shiju, morphological vocabulary includes affixation and reduplication; Morphological and structural modification of phonetic and phonetic changes in Sun Chaisseur; also includes affixation, reduplication, phonetic changes and conversion. The affix word formation in the Chinese language is the second most efficient after word formation. Affixation and semi-affixation are seen as two separate independent ways of word formation in linguistics. The main difference between these two methods is that in the first case, new words are generated by adding words and affixes that are based on the words in the language, and in the second case, the new words are formed using semicolons.

According to Zinc, affixation refers to the morphological method of word formation, and the semi-affixation refers to the lexical-morphological method of word formation. The issue of the difference between affixes and semi-affixes has been challenged by many linguists. It will be explored in detail by Frolova's studies and by the Chinese linguist Jen Sueelyan. Most modern Chinese word-formation affixes come from meaningful words. There are also many morphemes that have not yet come up with a way of translating from Chinese morphemes into affixes. They occupy the middle position between affixes and meaning-making morphemes, and are called semi-affixes.

Tao Lyan analyzes the neologisms' vocabulary and cites 18 prefixes and half prefixes and 54 suffixes and half suffixes. Of the 2,805 neologisms examined in the work, 93 (3.32%) new words, suffixes, and half suffixes generated 354 (12.62%) new words through prefixes and semi-prefixes.⁵⁴

From the above analysis, one can conclude that one of the most effective methods of word formation in Chinese is the large number of suffixes in affixes, which are the basis for their use as effective word-generators.

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